

Dietary Risk Assessment of Nitrates in Cyprus using up to date Food Consumption data (EU Menu)

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Περίληψη

Ο σκοπός της εκτίμησης κινδύνου ήταν να υπολογιστεί η διαιτητική πρόσληψη σε νιτρικά (NO_3^-) του πληθυσμού στην Κύπρο, να συγκριθεί η υπολογισθείσα πρόσληψη με την αποδεκτή ημερήσια πρόσληψη (Acceptable Daily Intake, ADI) που ισούται με 3.7 mg/kg βάρους σώματος (β.σ.) ανά ημέρα και να υπολογιστεί ο βαθμός συνεισφοράς των κυριότερων ομάδων τροφίμων στη συνολική διαιτητική έκθεση σε νιτρικά.

Τα στοιχεία κατανάλωσης τροφίμων λήφθηκαν από την Βάση Δεδομένων που δημιουργήθηκε από το EU Menu στο οποίο συμμετείχε η Κύπρος την περίοδο 2014-2018.

Τα αναλυτικά δεδομένα νιτρικών στα τρόφιμα παρήχθησαν στα πλαίσια του Επισήμου Ελέγχου που διενεργήθηκε στο Γενικό Χημείο του Κράτους (ΓΧΚ) από τα Εργαστήρια «Περιβαλλοντική κ.ά Επιβάρυνση Τροφίμων & Φυσικών Τοξινών» και «Πρόσθετα & Ειδικές Αναλύσεις Τροφίμων» για τα τρόφιμα και από το Εργαστήριο «Γενικές Αναλύσεις Νερών» για το πόσιμο νερό. Τα παραπάνω δεδομένα λήφθηκαν από τη Βάση Δεδομένων LIMS του ΓΧΚ.

Η κατηγοριοποίηση των τροφίμων έγινε με βάση το σύστημα κωδικοποίησης και περιγραφής των τροφίμων FoodEx1 της EFSA.

Η εκτίμηση της διαιτητικής έκθεσης σε νιτρικά του Κυπριακού πληθυσμού σε ατομικό επίπεδο, πραγματοποιήθηκε με τη χρήση του προσδιοριστικού μοντέλου “ImproRisk”, ενός εμπειρικού μοντέλου κατανομών βασισμένου στο Excel. Το μοντέλο αυτό αναπτύχθηκε για το ΓΧΚ από την εταιρεία IMPROVAST (www.improvast.com).

Η μέση και 95th percentile (P95) διαιτητικές τιμές πρόσληψης, με βάση τις διάμεσες τιμές συγκεντρώσεων νιτρικών, υπολογίστηκαν σε 787 και 2103 μg/kg β.σ. ανά ημέρα, αντίστοιχα. Με βάση τα παραπάνω συνάγεται ότι ο Κυπριακός πληθυσμός βρίσκεται σε ασφαλή επίπεδα έκθεσης. Αναμενόμενα, το μαρούλι και τα άλλα φυλλώδη λαχανικά (σπανάκι, ρόκα, γλιστρίδα, φύλλα παντζαριού) συνεισφεραν σε ποσοστό 34% επί της συνολικής έκθεσης σε νιτρικά, ακολουθούν οι πατάτες με ποσοστό 33% και τα βότανα (άνηθος, μαϊντανός, φύλλα σέλινου, φύλλα κόλιανδρου) με 10%.

Τέλος, οι αβεβαιότητες που επηρεάζουν την παραπάνω εκτίμηση της έκθεσης προσδιορίστηκαν και εκτιμήθηκαν.

Abstract

The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary nitrate (NO_3^-) intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the acceptable daily intake (ADI) of 3.7 mg/kg body weight (b.w.) per day and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary NO_3^- exposure.

Exposure assessment was performed by using the deterministic risk assessment model “ImproRisk” (<http://www.improrisk.com/>). The mean and 95th percentile dietary intake values, based on median nitrate concentrations, were 787 and 2103 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w. per day, respectively. According to the above results, the whole population of Cyprus is within safe exposure levels. Lettuce and other leafy vegetables (spinach, rocket/rucola, purslane, beet leaves) contributed nearly to 34%, followed by potatoes with 33%, and herbs (dill, parsley, celery leaves, coriander leaves) with 9%.

Finally, the uncertainties affecting the above exposure assessment were identified and assessed.

Materials and Methods

Food consumption data were obtained from the EU Menu project funded by EFSA and the dietary survey was carried out in the years 2014-2018. The consumption data was the result of a survey of **1641** participants (male and female). The survey covered all five cities of Cyprus, rural and urban regions, and also all days of the week and the four seasons. The population classes and the number of participants in each class were: [a] infants: 3-11 months (269), [b] toddlers: 12-35 months (279), [c] other children: 3-9 years (300), [d] adolescents: 10-17 years (274), [e] adults: 18-64 years (275) and [f] elderly: 65-74 years (264).

Nitrate occurrence data in food items were produced within the Official Control performed by the “Environmental and Other Food Contamination & Natural Toxins” Lab and the “Food Additives & Special Analyses of Food” Lab of the State General Laboratory (SGL). Nitrate occurrence data in drinking water were produced by the “General Water Analysis” Lab of SGL. The above data were extracted/collected from the Laboratory Management Information System (LIMS) of SGL.

The ImproRisk model was used in order to carry out the Nitrate dietary exposure.

Chronic Nitrate exposure was calculated using median concentrations and individual body weight and consumption amounts averaged over the days of the survey. The matching was done by using the EFSA FoodEx1 system ⁽¹⁾ at Level 2 and Level 3.

Results and Discussion

Nitrate occurrence data in food (n=906) and drinking water (n=8437) were extracted from LIMS for the years 2006-2018, and are shown in Table 1 and 2. Sample results below the limit of detection (LOD) or the limit of quantification (LOQ) were expressed as the upper bound (UB) value, so the actual LOD/LOQ were used in the calculations⁽²⁾.

Occurrence data were grouped according to twelve main food categories at FoodEx level 2, as shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Aggregated concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) for nitrate in food (FoodEx Level 2) in Cyprus (2006-2018).

FoodExL1_name	FoodExL2_name	No of Samples	$\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$
			median
Vegetables and vegetable products	Root vegetables	19	480
	Bulb vegetables	11	33
	Fruiting vegetables	27	10
	Brassica vegetables	15	351
	Leaf vegetables	282	1316
	Stem vegetables (Fresh)	58	1505,5
Starchy roots and tubers	Potatoes and potatoes products	60	179,8
Meat and meat products	Preserved meat	165	29,3
Milk and dairy products	Cheese	73	2
Drinking water	Drinking water	8437	3
Herbs, spices and condiments	Herbs	71	1353
Food for infants and small children	Ready-to-eat meal for infants and young children	125	56

Table 2: Aggregated concentrations (mg/kg) for Nitrate in food (FoodEx Level 3) in Cyprus (2006-2018)

FOODEX_L2_name	FOODEX_L3_name	UB median Occurrence (mg/kg)
Leaf vegetables		1316
	Lettuce, excluding Iceberg-type lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i>)	1083
	Iceberg-type lettuce	1112
	Rocket, Rucola (<i>Eruca sativa</i> , <i>Diplotaxis spec.</i>)	2243
	Spinach (fresh) (<i>Spinacia oleracea</i>)	1010
	Spinach (<i>Spinacia oleracea</i>), preserved, deep-frozen or frozen	3412
	Purslane (<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>)	1602
	Beet leaves (<i>Beta vulgaris</i>)	1602
Herbs		1353
	Dill, herb (<i>Anethum graveolens</i>)	1353
	Celery leaves (<i>Apium graveolens</i> var. <i>seccalinum</i>)	1353
	Parsley, herb (<i>Petroselinum crispum</i>)	1343
	Coriander leaves (classified as "Herbs, spices and condiments")	1748
Potatoes and potato products		180
Root vegetables		480
	Carrots (<i>Daucus carota</i>)	42
	Radishes (<i>Raphanus sativus</i> var. <i>sativus</i>)	1540
	Taro (<i>Colocasia</i> spp.)	480
Brassica vegetables		351
	Cauliflower (<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>botrytis</i>)	351
	Head cabbage (<i>Brassica oleracea</i> convar. <i>capitata</i>)	370
Fruiting vegetables		10
	Tomatoes (<i>Lycopersicon esculentum</i>)	10
	Peppers, paprika (<i>Capsicum annuum</i> , var. <i>grossum</i> and var. <i>longu</i>)	10
	Aubergines (egg plants) (<i>Solanum melongena</i>)	10
	Cucumbers (<i>Cucumis sativus</i>)	101
Stem vegetables (Fresh)		1506
	Celery (<i>Apium graveolens</i> var. <i>dulce</i>)	1506
Bulb vegetables		33
	Onions, bulb (<i>Allium cepa</i>)	33
	Spring onions, bulb (<i>Allium cepa</i>)	146
Ready-to-eat meal for infants and young children		56
	Ready-to-eat meal for children, meat and vegetables	52
	Ready-to-eat meal for children, vegetable-based	59
Preserved meat		29
Cheese		2
Drinking water		3

Chronic nitrate exposure was calculated using median nitrate concentrations and individual level body weight and consumption amounts averaged over the days of the survey for each individual. The matching was done by using the EFSA FoodEx system ⁽³⁾ at Level 2 and Level 3.

Based on median nitrate occurrence, mean and 95th percentile exposure were calculated as 787 and 2103 µg/kg b.w. per day, at 21% and 57% of the ADI, respectively (Table 3).

The above values are comparable to the corresponding exposure estimates (970 and 2410 µg/kg b.w, respectively), from the EFSA opinion on nitrates ⁽²⁾. It has to be noted, though, that the EFSA figures were calculated over the adolescent groups in the different European countries.

Furthermore, the exposure estimation in the current study is much lower than the estimate in an older study by Stavroulakis & Christofidou ⁽⁴⁾. Two reasons account for this finding: a) In the current study ImproRisk was configured to assess exposure at FoodEx level 3 as compared to level 2 for the older one and b) more accurate and detailed food consumption data (EU MENU) were used.

Table 3: Median nitrate exposure of the population in Cyprus.

	Mean	95 th percentile
Dietary exposure (µg/kg b.w./day)	787	2103
% ADI ¹	21	57

¹ ADI= 3700 µg/kg b.w./day

Figures 1 shows the distribution of exposure of the Cypriot population based on median occurrence. Substantially, the whole population exposure is within the ADI.

Figure 1: Probability distribution of nitrate exposure of the Cypriot population.

The contribution of the main food groups at FoodEx level 1, level 2 & level 3 to the total nitrate exposure is shown in **Figure 2**. Vegetables contribute to 56% to the nitrate intake. 34% (61% of the exposure contribution due to vegetables) and 16% (47% of the exposure due to leafy vegetables) of the total nitrate intake account for leafy vegetables and lettuce, respectively.

Furthermore, the contribution of potatoes and herbs (dill, parsley, celery leaves, coriander leaves) to the total intake was significant (33% and 10%, respectively).

These results are consistent with the EFSA findings ⁽²⁾.

Figure 2: Contribution of food categories at FoodEx level 1, level 2 & level 3 to the total exposure to nitrates (median occurrence).

In **Figure 3**, the exposure of each population class is shown. It was found that toddlers, infants and other children had higher exposure than adults. Although, infants consume less food contaminated with nitrates, they showed high exposure due to their higher ratio of consumed food to body weight, as compared to adults.

Figure 3. Mean exposure by population class.

Figure 4 illustrates the mean exposure to nitrate by gender and population class. It was found that there is no significant difference between men and women in all population classes. This is because the population in Cyprus has the same food consumption habits both in terms of gender (men-women) and between different classes of the population and also the foodstuffs that are contaminated by nitrate are consumed by all population classes.

Figure 4. Mean exposure by gender and population class.

In **Figure 5**, the exposure of population by geographical area is shown. It was found that Pafos and Limassol had higher exposure than Larnaca, Ammochostos and Nicosia.

Figure 5. Mean exposure by geographical area.

Uncertainties

The evaluation of the uncertainties in the exposure assessment of nitrate has been performed following the guidance of the Opinion of the Scientific Committee related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment ⁽⁵⁾. Table 4 presents a summary of uncertainties, highlighting the main sources of uncertainty and providing an estimate whether each source of uncertainty is likely to lead to an over- or under-estimation of the calculated dietary exposure.

Table 4: Summary of qualitative evaluation of the impact of uncertainties on the dietary exposure to nitrates.

Sources of uncertainty	Direction ¹
Uncertainties regarding the influence of food processing and/or cooking on the nitrate levels in the processed food – ImproRisk limitation	+
Uncertainty of the analytical measurements	+/-
Uncertainty about the representativeness of samples concerning, country of origin, size, seasonal differences, specific type of vegetable	+/-
Extrapolation uncertainties affecting the estimation of food consumption	+
Uncertainty in recording food types	+/-
Measurement error in amounts of food consumed	+/-
Measurement error in individual body weights	+/-

¹ + = uncertainty with potential to cause over-estimation of exposure; - = uncertainty with potential to cause under-estimation of exposure

The exposure scenario used in this study is based in raw products. The exposure model used (i.e. ImproRisk) does not take into account the possible changes of the nitrate content due to processing of food commodities, which may lead to an overestimation of the exposure ^(4, 5).

Furthermore, a number of uncertainties can be identified regarding the selection of parameters, such as the estimation of nitrate concentrations in food commodities and selection of consumption data.

The uncertainty related to the representativeness of the samples is taken into account as nitrate concentration levels are affected by season and type of vegetable.

Some potentially important extrapolation uncertainties arise since an individual survey of food consumption is used to estimate dietary exposure over a timescale longer than the survey duration ⁽⁵⁾.

Conclusions

Median dietary nitrate exposure at individual level of the Cypriot population was calculated as 787 and 2103 µg/kg b.w./day for mean and high consumers, respectively. Nitrate intake was estimated to be lower than the ADI (3700 µg/kg b.w./day), for the whole Cyprus population.

Lettuce and other leafy vegetables (spinach, rocket/rucola, purslane, beet leaves) showed the highest contribution (34%) to nitrate exposure. Furthermore, the contribution of potatoes to the total intake was significant (33%). Also herbs contributed nearly 10% to the total nitrate intake of the population.

ImproRisk, with the capacity to calculate individual exposure at FoodEx1 level 3, resulted in more refined and accurate exposure estimations for nitrate as compared to a similar older study⁽⁴⁾.

References

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